

Nutrient Management for Rice Using Goal Programming

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Abstract. A very nutritious grain, rice is thought to be consumed by two-thirds of the world's population, ranking higher than many other foods. The right combination of fertilizers must be applied to the soil in order to boost rice crop output. The soil conditions will improve with suitable fertilizers, allowing for the growth of good nutrient crops. When N(nitrogen), P(Phosphorous), K(potassium), S(Sulphur), Cu(copper), Zn(zinc), and B(boron) are included in a fertilizer blend, it is complete. The ideal fertilizer mixture for rice production in Karnataka is identified in this research in order to demonstrate a goal programming technique for nutrient management. A collection of data was used to determine the effectiveness and efficiency of the proposed model. The proportion of the nutrients has been determined using game theory. The results of the formulation specify that all objectives have been met. The suggested paradigm is adaptable in terms of the goal priority.

Key words: Goal programming, Game Theory, Fertilizer Combinations, Agriculture.

1. Introduction

In Indian agriculture, rice plays a critical role. One of the most significant staple food crops in the world, rice is grown in at least 114 different nations in a variety of climates. With the present population growth rate by the year 2022, there will be a need for about 51.8 million tons of rice. Production growth in all ecosystems is approaching a peak as population expansion keeps driving up demand for rice. By using better agronomic practices and utilizing high yielding varieties, rice output can be increased. Karnataka is situated in the southwest region of India. The Indian State of Karnataka is situated between latitudes of 11°30' and 18°30' North and between latitudes of 74° and 78°30' East. It is located on a plateau in the western Deccan Peninsular region of India, in which the Western Ghats and Eastern Ghats join to form a complex. The soil types are classified into six categories based on their suitability for agriculture in Karnataka (fig 1). Red, lateritic, black, alluvia-colluvial, forest, and coastal soils. Red soils include red clay, red gravelly clay, red loam, and red gravelly loam. Gravelly soil, loose soil, and basalt deposits are examples of black soil. Lateritic soils include gravelly lateritic soil and lateritic soil. Deep, medium, and shallow black soils are all types of black soil. Saline, saline-sodic, and non-saline alluvio-colluvial soils. Brown-colored Forest soil Coastal soil types include coastal alluvial and coastal laterite soil. The total irrigated area of Karnataka is 40.32 lakh hectares. For the years 2021-2022, Karnataka state consumed 790.28, 386.78, and 330.32 thousand tons of fertilizer nutrients N(nitrogen), P(phosphorus), and K(potassium). Higher-than-required applications of N, P and K are likely to have a variety of impacts on crops and significantly reduce their yields. Therefore, it is essential to create the best fertilizer mixes for applying nutrients to the soil to sustainably grow food grains. This prevents harm to the health of the soil. This enhances the economic situation of farmers by increasing the output of goods with a higher cost-benefit ratio.

Figure -1: Different types of soils in Karnataka

There may be multiple goals in problems involving nitrogen management and the best fertilizer combination. The decision-making process often considers meeting nutrient requirements and reducing costs of the fertilizers.

In a model for executive compensation, Charnes, Cooper, and Ferguson [1] in 1955 initially introduced GP. Early financial studies included Lee and Lerro [2] in 1973 used GP model for mutual fund portfolio selection and Ignizio [3] in 1976 implemented branch and bound algorithm, which formalized the notion of multiple objectives in capital budgeting. Romero [4] used the GP approach in 1986 to address issues with agricultural management. Optimization of an MCDM model's solution in agricultural planning implemented by Ghosh. D [5]. The optimal fertilizer mixture allocation for rice product in the years 2008–2009 was discussed by A. Sargazi et. al [6]. Dorothy et. al [7] developed Goal programming for the control of nutrients in rice production. Debasis Ghosh et. al [8] represented goal programming for sugarcane fertilizers mix problem. R.K. Jana et. al [9] used FGP based genetic algorithm for maintaining the soil health and increasing the production of rice yield. Nur Hanani et. al [10] developed goal programming to fertilizer combinations for pineapple production. J. Ramesh Babu et. al [11] used the LP, GP, and WGP models to determine the most cost-effective fertilizer combinations. Ines Minguez et. al [4] determined the fertilizer combination for sugar beet production by goal programming with the help of penalty function. Nasruddin. H et. al [12] created a goal programming problem for Malaysian pineapple cultivation's nutrient management. Goal programming model was implemented by Khairil B. H. et. al [13] for fertilizer compounds and minimizing cucumber production costs. The GP model for fertilizer combinations for a chilly plantation is developed by Suhalia Safiai et. al [14] Preemptive GP was utilized by Rida Agustina et. al [15] to regulate palm nutrition levels. Girmay et. al [16] apply the GP for compost management to a teff plantation. Zebene et. al [17] used a goal programming model to design a balanced and cost-effective nutrient mix for teff plantations. To increase rice yield and quality, Mo Li et. al [18] utilized fuzzy goal programming for fertilizer mixture and water reducibility. In this study, the optimal fertilizers mixture has been identified in order to determine the nutrient demand for rice production using a priority-based linear GP technique. Sensitivity analysis on the price of several fertiliser combinations with varied production levels has been done in order to find the optimal option. Finally, by using the Game Theory approach, the ideal combination has been identified. The technique has been used to identify the ideal fertilizers mix for rice production in Karnataka during the Kharif season.

2. Model Formulation

The general goal programming model is given by

$$\text{Minimize } \sum_{i=1}^m P_i (C^- + C^+)$$

Subjected to

$$\sum_{j=1}^n M_{ij} F_j + C^- - C^+ = K_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, m, j = 1, 2, \dots, n \text{ and } F_j, C^-, C^+ \geq 0 \text{ for all } i, j$$

Where M_{ij} is the coefficient for the i th goal in j th variable, F_j is the decision variable of j , the value of right-hand side is K_i , from the i th goal the underachievement of negative deviational variable and overachievement of positive deviational variable are C^- and C^+ respectively. The deviational factors (C^- & C^+) that indicate each goal or subgoal comprise most of the objective function. The deviational factors are shown as deviations from each objective or subgoal, both positive and negative. Considering the proportional relevance or priority (P_i) given to them, the objective function accordingly changes to the minimization of these deviations.

Using the general GP model, the following variables, constants, and coefficients create the model for the problem.

F_n = combination of different fertilizer mixes where $n = 1, 2, 3 \dots N$.

R_n = cost for the fertilizers.

M_n = quantity of nutrient in the fertilizers (x_n).

LL_n = lower limit of nutrient.

UL_n = upper limit of nutrient.

C_f = total cost of the fertilizers.

A is the rice production per unit of land area.

The factors u and v determine how much fertilizers are used per unit of crop production.

Goals:

(i) Minimizing expenditure: An estimated fertilizers cost C_f should be included to avoid any additional costs for the year.

$$\sum_{n=1}^N R_n F_n + C^- - C^+ = C_f$$

(ii) Maintain at least minimum amount of nutrients: To produce a healthy yield from the rice farm, there should be at least a minimal amount of nutrients in the fertilizers combination.

$$\sum_{n=1}^N M_n F_n + L^- - L^+ = LL_n$$

(iii) Aim to control the maximum limit of nutrients: To prevent the excess use of nutrient in the fertilizer mix.

$$\sum_{n=1}^N M_n F_n + U^- - U^+ = UL_n$$

(iv) Maintenance of good number of yield crops: Under typical circumstances, the yield of crops directly correlates to the amount of nutrients applied to the soil. In other words, the yield can be defined as $A = ux + v$. In any real-world circumstance, it is challenging to ascertain what values u and v should be. This form, however, appeared rational and can be dictated by different communications between fertilizer used in mixture, each of which has unique impacts on the soil and crop output. To determine the parameter values of u and v , the following must be measured and taken into account. In the same way that simultaneous equations are solved for linear functions, this can be accomplished by specifying the connection between 2-point estimates.

$$u \sum_{n=1}^N F_n + A^- - A^+ = A - v$$

(v) Optimization of primary nutrient to the second season: Nearly three months a year are dedicated to rice planting. It's possible that fertilizers from the previous season weren't utilized to their maximum potential (p). Therefore, it may not be necessary to apply all of the basic nutrient supplies that were treated during the earlier season in the next one. On the basis of last season's use of $(s - f)$ fertilizers, it is presumed that the primary nutrients were applied.

$$\left(1 - \frac{p}{100}\right) \sum_{n=f+1}^s M_n F_n \leq \left(\frac{p}{100}\right) \sum_{n=1}^f M_n F_n$$

3. Game model

We used various estimations ($C_{f_1}, C_{f_2} \dots C_{f_i}$) for the expenses of various fertilizers mixtures, which are choices made by agriculturalists based on the budgetary resources available at the time. According to the demand, farmers can choose another rice yield ($A_1, A_2 \dots A_j$) for that season. The fertilizer combination's total nutrient content per square foot of land that must be applied is displayed in Table 1 as $Tn_{ij} = \sum_n^{10} F_n M_n$. Hence, the j th decision on the requirement for yield are related to the i th decision regarding the availability of funds. Here, C_{f_i} represents the total cost of the fertilizer combination in accordance with the choice i regarding the fund's availability, and A_j represents the crop harvest in accordance with the j decision regarding the demand for its yield. The minimum of i (maximum of j) of Tn_{ij} is equal to maximum of j (minimum of i) of Tn_{ij} i. e the saddle point of the game model which shows the strategy of optimal solution to the farmers to take choice on the fertilizer mixtures.

The game model's saddle point, $\min(\max) Tn_{ij} = \max(\min) Tn_{ij}$, will provide the optimal procedure of action for the farmer to choose the best fertilizer mix.

Depending on the availability of funds (i)	Depending on customer demand					
	A_1	A_2		A_j		A_j
C_{f_1}	Tn_{11}	Tn_{12}		Tn_{1j}		Tn_j
C_{f_2}	Tn_{21}	Tn_{22}		Tn_{2j}		Tn_{2j}
....						
C_{f_i}	Tn_{i1}	Tn_{i2}		Tn_{ij}		Tn_{ij}
....						
C_{f_l}	Tn_{l1}	Tn_{l2}		Tn_{lj}		Tn_{lj}

4. Data Collection

Indian State of Karnataka, our fertilizer combination strategy is for the production of rice. The harvest of rice in 2021–2022 was 3435 kg/ha on 11 lakh hectares of land. Farmers at the state and national levels have been using progressively high yield varieties of crops and growing crop strengths with high levels of N-P-K fertilizers,

particularly over the past forty years, to meet the nation's continuously rising need for food grains. These three important nutrients were necessary for the soil to grow rice. The most important major limitations for rice production are N and P, however, K is also a limiting factor in many of the state's districts. Therefore, it is impossible to grow rice with a high yield without using the correct, balanced N-P-K fertilizer. To learn more about how rice transplants affect growth and yields, an examination into the N-P-K requirements was conducted. Applying nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium using various fertilizers mixtures, as shown in Table 2, will result in the highest grain production possible. The Soil Testing Laboratory of the Indian Council of Agricultural Research recommends that the highest and lowest requirements of those nutrients be 150 to 180 kg per hectore of nitrogen, 110 to 140 kg per hectore of phosphorous, and 90 to 130 kg per hectore of potassium for our research region. Information for the previous year 2021-2022 has been gathered from the Directorate of Agriculture, Government of Karnataka, to illustrate the model. Table 2 displays the prices (R_n) and combinations of fertilizers (M_n) that are readily available. The use of Nitrogen, Phosphorous and Potassium using various fertilizers is shown in Table 2.

Table 2- Fertilizer variables, cost and percentage of nutrients used.

Fertilizer (kg)	F_1	F_2	F_3	F_4	F_5	F_6	F_7	F_8	F_9	F_{10}
Nitrogen (%)	46				18	20	28	15	10	14
Phosphorous (%)		16			46	20	28	15	26	35
Potassium (%)			60	50				15	26	14
Cost (Rs/kg)	9	8	20	20	30	17	34	22	24	30

In Table 2

$F_1 = \text{CH}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}$ (Urea)

$F_2 = \text{SSP}$ (Single super Phosphate)

$F_3 = \text{Potassium Chloride KCL}$ (Muriate of Potash)

$F_4 = \text{Muriate of Potash}$ (Potassium Sulphate (K_2SO_4))

$F_5 = \text{Di Ammonium Phosphate}$ (DAP)

$F_6 = \text{Ammonium Nitro Phosphate}$

$F_7 = \text{Urea Ammonia Phosphate}$

$F_8 = \text{Nitro Phosphate with Potash}$

$F_9 = \text{Nitro Phosphate with Potash}$

$F_{10} = \text{Nitro Phosphate with Potash}$

Goal programming model for the problem:

Cost Constraints: The total cost for the fertilizers

$$\sum_{n=1}^N R_n F_n + C^- - C^+ = C_f$$

Fertilizer Constraints: Upper limit of the fertilizers and lower limit of the fertilizer

$$\sum_{n=1}^N M_n F_n + L_1^- - L_1^+ = 150 \text{ (Nitrogen } \geq 150)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^N M_n F_n + L_2^- - L_2^+ = 110 \text{ (Phosphorous } \geq 110)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^N M_n F_n + L_3^- - L_3^+ = 90 \text{ (Potassium } \geq 90)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^N M_n F_n + U_1^- - U_1^+ = 180 \text{ (Nitrogen } \leq 180)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^N M_n F_n + U_2^- - U_2^+ = 140 \text{ (Phosphorous } \leq 140)$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^N M_n F_n + U_3^- - U_3^+ = 130 \text{ (Potassium } \leq 130)$$

Crop goal: Here u and v are estimated and presented based on the knowledge of farmers.

$$3.14 \sum_{n=1}^N F_n + A_1 - A_2 = A - 1.50$$

Primary nutrient: Through the usage of F_6, F_7, F_8, F_9 and F_{10} it is expected that a maximum of 40% of the primary nutrient necessities were applied over the last year. The restrictions can be expressed as

$$-18F_1 - 7F_5 + 12F_6 + 17F_7 + 6F_9 + 8F_{10} + N_1^- - N_1^+ = 0 \text{ for nitrogen}$$

$$-6F_2 - 18F_5 + 12F_6 + 17F_7 + 9F_8 + 15F_9 + 21F_{10} + P_1^- - P_1^+ = 0 \text{ for Phosphorous}$$

$$-24F_3 - 20F_4 + 9F_8 + 16F_9 + 8F_{10} + Pt_1^- - Pt_1^+ = 0 \text{ for Potassium}$$

Objective function:

$$\text{Min } Z = P_1(L_1^- + L_2^- + L_3^-) + P_2(N_1^+ + P_1^+ + Pt_1^+) + P_3(C_2 + U_1^+ + U_2^+ + U_3^+ + A_2)$$

5. Results

Using LiPS software, the issue has been worked through. Following the completion of thirteen to fourteen

iterative steps for each set of projected cost and yield target values, the findings are as follows. Table 3 presents the decision-payoff matrix under various circumstances. Table 4 presents the top accomplishments in relation to the best choice. The ideal strategy for a farmer to choose the right fertilizers combination is implied by the saddle point, which is $\min(\max) Tn_{ij} = \max(\min) Tn_{ij} = 414$.

Table 3-The best choice under different circumstances

Depending on the availability of funds (<i>i</i>)	Depending on customer demand		
	3500 kg/ha	3590 kg/ha	Maximum j
3550	259	273	259
3500	202	222	202
3450	200	211	200
3400	414	435	414
Minimum i	414	435	

Table 4- Achievement of Priorities

As a result, the corresponding solutions are

$F_1 = 166$ kg/ha, $F_4 = 196$ kg/ha, $F_5 = 80$ kg/ha, $F_7 = 265$ kg/ha, $F_9 = 82$ kg/ha, $F_{10} = 16$ kg/ha.

In this case, the recommended fertilizer rate is 414 kg/ha, which contains 176 kg per hectare of N (nitrogen), 138 kg per hectare of P (phosphorus), and 122 kg per hectare of K (potassium). The price of the recommended fertilizer mixture is Rs. 3400 /ha, and the expected yield is 3500 kg per hectare. Additionally, it has been noted that the above mixture increased the rice production for the 2021–2022 season from 3435 to 3500 kg per hectare.

6. Conclusion

In place of conventional optimization methods based on linear programming, the procedure for the best fertilizer mixtures provided in this work offers new insights. It might be helpful for farm organizers who can help agriculturalists on fertilizer and nutrient mixtures. This work makes an effort to use the GP technique to address the nutrient management issue. Although the research for rice cultivation using nutrient management is restricted to a certain agro-climatic situation of Karnataka, it can be summed up that the production of rice can be significantly enhanced while maintaining soil fertility.

7. Acknowledgement

For the resources supplied to conduct the research, the authors thank REVA University for their cooperation.

8. Conflict of interest

No conflicts of interest.

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